

Relationship between agronomic characters with yield of mungbean in wetland

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ABSTRACT

Mungbean is one of the important cash crops legumes in Indonesia which is rich in digestible protein, and can be planted in wetland during the dry season or on dry fields during the rainy season. The aim of this study was to determine the relationship among mungbean genotypes based on agronomic characters and identify the direct influence of agronomic character to yield diverse mungbean genotypes. The experiment was conducted in Kendalpayak Research Station in Malang during the dry season 2016. The material used was 200 genotypes of mungbean from Indonesian Legumes and Tuber Crops Research Institute (ILETRI) germplasm. The variables observed were plant height, days to flowering (50%), days to maturity, ratio of vegetative and generative (V/G) phase, number of branches, number of cluster, number of pods/cluster, pod length, number of seeds/pod, 100-seed weight, and seed yield per plant. Data were analyzed using correlation and path analysis. The results showed that number of branches, number of cluster, number of pod per cluster, number of seeds per pod have a significant positive correlation to mungbean yield. The direct effect of number of cluster on seed yield was the highest among others (0.676), thus it can be concluded that direct selection by using number of cluster is considered effective to obtain high seed yield on mungbean.

Keywords: correlation, path analysis, yield, *Vigna radiata*

INTRODUCTION

Mungbean is one of important cash crop legumes in Indonesia. Its position is in third rank as the most important food crop legumes, after soybean and groundnut. Mungbean has special characteristics, due to its short life (early maturity), rich protein content and excellent digestibility. Mungbean plays a role in improving food quality because of their high nutritional content. According to Kim et al. (2015), mungbean represents a cheap source of carbohydrates and high-quality protein, folate, and iron. The demand for mungbean continues to increase along with the increasing number of Indonesian population and the growing development of the food processing industry. During the last ten years (2003-2013) the mungbean harvest areas

decreased by 30.85%, this led to a decrease in mungbean production by 24.18 (Indonesian Statistics Agency, 2016).

In Indonesia, mungbean can be planted in wetland during the dry season or on dry fields during the rainy season. According to Purwaningrahayu et al. (2013), mungbean is generally planted in the dry season after upland rice or corn. In wet climates, mungbean is cultivated with planting patterns upland rice maize/soybean-mungbean, or maize-soybean-mungbean. In wetland, mungbean are planted after paddy with the pattern of planting paddy-paddy-mungbean.

In choosing mungbean varieties, farmers generally consider the productivity, consumer preference, and the grain price (Trustinah et al., 2014). Planting high yielding of mungbean varieties have proven to increase the grain productivity in most areas. Yield is a complex character associated with various contributing characters which are interrelated among themselves (Garg et al., 2017). Some of the yield components are highly interrelated. On the other hand, grain yield is determined by many genetical as well as environmental factors that are interdependent (Canci and Toker, 2014).

Various studies of the character of plants related to the yield has been done a lot. Younis et al. (2008) reported that positive result of Lentil plants (*Lens culinaris* Medik) was affected directly by days to flowering, plant height, number of main branches, biological results, harvest index, and weight of 100 seeds. Mahbub et al. (2015) reported that plant height, pod length, number of seeds per pod, number of pods per plant, hundred seed weight, branches per plant and number of seeds per pod showed significant positive genotypic and phenotypic correlation with soybean yield. Begum (2013) reported that yield of mungbean had significant genotypic correlation with days to pods formation. Hapsari (2014) reported that the phenotypic correlation between 1000 seeds weight and pod length with seed yield were positive significant with yield.

With only using correlation analysis between yields with yield components, sometimes mis-interpretations occur because interrelated components are correlated. Splitting correlation into direct and indirect effects, therefore, would provide more meaningful interpretation. Thus correlation in combination with path coefficient analysis is required to assess quantitatively direct and indirect influences of yield attributing character (Alom et al., 2014). Therefore the aim of this study was to determine the relationship of agronomic characters with yield and identification the direct influence of agronomic character to yield diverse mungbean genotype.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at Kendalpayak Research Station, Indonesian Legumes and Tuber Research Institute (ILETRI) located in Malang, East Java (8° 2' 56.4" S, 112° 37' 30"E) in 2016. A total of 200 accessions of mungbean germplasm from ILETRI's collection were used in this study. Each accession was planted in plant spacing of 40 x 15 cm with plot size 4.5 m², and two plant was maintained in each hole. The variable observed were plant height, days to flowering (50%), days to maturity, ratio of vegetative and generative (V/G) phase, number of branches, number of cluster, number of pods/cluster, pod length, number of seeds/pod, 100-seed weight, and seed yield per plant.

Data were analysis using correlation and path analysis. Correlation analysis were done using Minitab 14 program to determine the relationship between agronomic components and yield. Direct and indirect contributions of various characters to yield were calculated through path coefficient analysis according to Singh and Chaudary (1979).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Agronomic characters

Variation is the first requirement for selection in plant breeding (Canci and Taker, 2014). The agronomic characters observed in this research have quite high diversity. This is reflected in the fairly large range of minimum and maximum values. Range of value, mean performance, and standard deviation of mungbean accessions of characters studied are presented in Table 1. Standard deviation of 11 observed characters ranged 0.1-19.4. Plant height varied from 22.5-138 cm with an average 83.1 cm. Days to flowering varied from 31-57 days with an average 40.7 days. Days to maturity varied from 60-97 days with an average 77.1 days. Ratio of vegetative and generative (V/G) phase varied from 0.4-0.7 with an average 0.5. It means that in this study the genotype relatively has the same duration of vegetative and generative phases.

In yield components, number of branch varied from 0-5 with an average 1.8. Number of cluster varied from 3.8-18.8 with an average 9. The number of pods per cluster varied from 1-6 with an average 2.7. Pod length varied from 5.9-11.7 cm with an average 8.8 cm. Number of seeds per pod varied from 5.6-14.1 with an average 11.2. Seed size varied from 3.4-7.3 g/100 seeds with an average 4.7 g/100 seeds. Seed yield per plant varied from 1-17.8 g with an average 9 g.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of 200 mungbean accessions, 2016

Characters	Range	Mean	St_Dev
Plant height (cm)	22.5-138	83.1	19.4

Days to flowering	31-57	40.7	4.9
Days to maturity	60-97	77.1	10.1
Ratio V/G	0.4-0.7	0.5	0.1
Number of branches per plant	0-5	1.8	0.8
Number of cluster	3.8-18.8	9.0	3.9
Number of pod per cluster	1-6	2.7	0.7
Pod length (cm)	5.9-11.7	8.8	0.9
Number of seeds per pod	5.6-14.1	11.2	1.2
100-seed weight (g)	3.4-7.3	4.7	1.0
Seed yield per plant (g)	1-17.8	9.0	3.2

Coefficient correlation and path analysis

Correlation is useful to assess the strength of the relationship between two or more characters. The correlation between quantitative characters and yield has an important meaning in selection activities of breeding program. In this research, there was significant positive correlation between yield and agronomic parameters was number of branch ($r=0.227^{**}$), number of cluster ($r=0.418^{**}$), number of pod/cluster ($r=0.393^{**}$), and number of seeds/pod ($r=0.28^{**}$) (Table 2). This indicated that increase of yield is directly related to the increase number of branch, number of cluster, number of pod/cluster, and number of seeds/pod. These results are in conformity by Makeen et al. (2007); Hemavathy et al. (2015) for number of seeds per pod with and by Saeed et al. (2007) for number of branch.

However, days to flowering ($r=-0.308^{**}$), days to maturity ($r=-0.139^{**}$), and ratio of vegetative and generative (V/G) phase ($r=-0.19^{**}$) were negatively correlated to yield. This result suggested that the importance of short duration genotypes. Similar finding were also reported for days to flowering and maturity by Trustinah and Iswanto (2014); Hapsari (2014) and Garg et al. (2017).

Table 2. Coefficient correlation between agronomic characters with yield

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8	X9	X10
X2	0.591**									
X3	0.669**	0.691**								
X4	-0.19**	0.289**	-0.487**							
X5	0.091	0.208**	0.18*	-0.002						
X6	0.434**	0.367**	0.446**	-0.16*	0.548**					
X7	-0.144*	-0.375**	-0.257**	-0.109	-0.252**	-0.158*				
X8	-0.065	0.009	-0.117	0.163*	-0.146*	-0.297**	-0.139*			
X9	0.293**	0.061	0.213**	-0.216**	-0.148*	0.023	0.265**	0.169*		
X10	-0.561**	-0.48**	-0.579**	0.199**	-0.314**	-0.488**	0.03	0.438**	-0.184**	
X11	-0.069	-0.308**	-0.139*	-0.19**	0.227**	0.418**	0.393**	-0.063	0.28**	0.042

Note: X1=plant height, X2=days to flowering, X3=days to maturity, X4=ratio V/G, X5=number of branch, X6=number of cluster, X7=number of pod/cluster, X8=pod length, X9=number of seeds/pod, X10=100 seed weight, X11=yield.

The association relationship of mungbean yield and the yield components has an important meaning, especially in relation to selection criteria. But these characters are not automatically suggested as single criteria

for selection. This is because the strength of the relationship measured through the correlation coefficient cannot reveal the extent of the role of the character itself to the final result. It can happen that a certain character has a high correlation to yield, but after further analysis it turns out that the relationship is due to indirect influence through other characters. To study the direct and the indirect effect between the yield and the yield components, the path analysis was conducted.

Number of cluster showed a high direct positive effect ($P=0.677$) on yield (Table 3). This character also has a significant positive correlation with yield. These results indicated that number of clusters has a true relationship to the yield and direct selection of these characters will be considering effective. Number of branch and number of pod per cluster are also having positive correlation and direct effect. However, the coefficient of direct effect was small, so it can be ignored. According to Sumarno and Zuraida (2006), competitive and compensative between morphologically characters regularly cause the variable observed to be less consistent.

Table 3. The path coefficient analysis of the yield components of mungbean

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8	X9	X10	r
X1	-0.061	-0.432	0.275	-0.069	0.013	0.294	-0.046	-0.003	0.083	-0.121	-0.069
X2	-0.036	-0.731	0.284	0.105	0.029	0.248	-0.121	0.000	0.017	-0.104	-0.308**
X3	-0.041	-0.505	0.411	-0.177	0.025	0.302	-0.083	-0.006	0.060	-0.125	-0.139*
X4	0.012	-0.211	-0.200	0.363	0.000	-0.108	-0.035	0.008	-0.061	0.043	-0.19**
X5	-0.006	-0.152	0.074	-0.001	0.139	0.371	-0.081	-0.008	-0.042	-0.068	0.227**
X6	-0.027	-0.268	0.183	-0.058	0.076	0.677	-0.051	-0.015	0.007	-0.105	0.418**
X7	0.009	0.274	-0.105	-0.040	-0.035	-0.107	0.323	-0.007	0.075	0.006	0.393**
X8	0.004	-0.007	-0.048	0.059	-0.020	-0.201	-0.045	0.052	0.048	0.095	-0.063
X9	-0.018	-0.045	0.087	-0.078	-0.021	0.016	0.086	0.009	0.284	-0.040	0.28**
X10	0.034	0.351	-0.238	0.072	-0.044	-0.330	0.010	0.023	-0.052	0.216	0.042

Note: Bold figure indicated the direct effect, X1=plant height, X2=days to flowering, X3=days to maturity, X4=ratio V/G, X5=number of branch, X6=number of cluster, X7=number of pod/cluster, X8=pod length, X9=number of seeds/pod, X10=100 seed weight.

CONCLUSIONS

Some agronomic characters such as number of branches, number of cluster, number of pod per cluster, number of seeds per pod have a significant positive correlation to mungbean yield. The direct effect of number of cluster on yield was the highest among others, thus it can be concluded that direct

selection by using number of cluster is considered effective to obtain high yield of mungbean.

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